

On Ranking Measures of Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number

*A. Gokul Priyan, **N. Uma

*M.Sc. Student, Department of Mathematics, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts and Science (Formerly SNR Sons College), Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu.

**Asso. Prof. & Head, Department of Mathematics, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts and Science (Formerly SNR Sons College), Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu.

ORCID: [0000-0003-4355-2916](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4355-2916)

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10686958

Abstract

A new approach of Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number (*HIFMN*) is studied in this paper. Few Ranking Measures of *HIFMN* are introduced, so that their (membership and non-membership) values are converted into crisp data for the comparison and analysis purpose. Numerical Examples are also demonstrated in order to justify that the new ranking measures of *HIFMN* are concrete as they satisfy the general ranking measure properties.

Keywords: Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets; Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Numbers; Heptagonal Fuzzy Number; Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Number Ranking Measure.

1. Introduction

In the majority of the real-life problem, the information available are insufficient and for this type of problem **Zadeh**[13] introduced the Fuzzy set consisting of membership functions. Ranking of fuzzy numbers plays an important role in decision making process and **Jain** [4] was the one to initiate for ranking fuzzy numbers for decision making. Later, Intuitionistic fuzzy set was introduced by **Atanasov** [2], which involves membership and non-membership functions. Once the Fuzzy Number was defined by **Dijkmanet** [3], Ranking the fuzzy numbers plays an important aspect of decision making in a fuzzy environment for practical applications. **Chen** [8] introduces the concept of ordering (ranking) value of each fuzzy number. Later many researches have defined various ranking function for Intuitionistic fuzzy numbers and verified its axioms. For ranking the Fuzzy number and Intuitionistic fuzzy number with efficiency, the Triangular, Trapezoidal, Pentagonal, Hexagonal and Octagonal numbers were frequently considered.

In order to study the multiset concepts, first **Yagar** [12] proposed the fuzzy multiset. Then, **Shinoj & John** [9,10] introduced Intuitionistic fuzzy multi set and **Rajarajeshwari & Uma**

[5,6,7] introduced some distance and similarity measures for Intuitionistic fuzzy multi sets (*IFMS*). Later, Ranking measures of Fuzzy multi numbers (*FMN*) were studied by Vivek et al. [11] for Triangular, Trapezoidal, Pentagonal, Hexagonal and Octagonal numbers.

This paper concerns with the study of Heptagonal Number in multiset concepts and is categorized as follows: the section 2 concerns with the Heptagonal fuzzy number (*HFN*) and Heptagonal intuitionistic fuzzy number (*HIFN*) along with some preliminary concepts needed for the study. The Heptagonal intuitionistic fuzzy multi number (*HIFMN*) was presented in the section 3. Few methods of Ranking measures of *HIFMN* were introduced in the section 4. And in section 5, the analysis of these methods using numerical examples were verified to check whether the defined ranking measures satisfy the general ranking properties.

2. Preliminaries

The basic concepts and definitions are reviewed in this section

Definition 2.1

If X is a collection of objects denoted by z , then the **fuzzy set** A is defined as set of ordered pair $A = \{(z, \mu_A(z)) / z \in X\}$, where $\mu_A(z)$ is called a membership function of z of the fuzzy set A . The membership function maps each element of X to a membership value between 0 and 1.

Definition 2.2

Let X is a collection of objects denoted by z then the **intuitionistic fuzzy set** A is defined as $A = \{(z, \mu_A(z), \gamma_A(z)) / z \in X\}$ where $\mu_A(z)$ is a membership function of z in X , and $\gamma(z)$ is a non-membership function of z in X and this both maps each element of X between 0 and 1 such that $0 \leq \mu_A(z) + \gamma_A(z) \leq 1$

Definition 2.3

A **heptagonal fuzzy number** is a 7 tuples $A_H = (a, b, c, d, e, f, g)$ where a, b, c, d, e, f and g are real numbers and $a \leq b \leq c \leq d \leq e \leq f \leq g$

$$\mu_A(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z-a}{b-a} \right] & a \leq z \leq b \\ \frac{1}{2} & b \leq z \leq c \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z-c}{d-c} \right] & c \leq z \leq d \\ 1 & z = d \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{e-z}{e-d} \right] & d \leq z \leq e \\ \frac{1}{2} & e \leq z \leq f \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{g-z}{g-f} \right] & f \leq z \leq g \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Figure 1- Heptagonal Fuzzy Number

Definition 2.4

A heptagonal Intuitionistic fuzzy number is 7 tuples

$$A_H = \{ (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7), (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5, b_6, b_7) \}$$

where $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7, b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5, b_6, b_7$ are real numbers

and $b_1 \leq a_1 \leq b_2 \leq a_2 \leq b_3 \leq a_3 \leq b_4 = a_4 \leq a_5 \leq b_5 \leq a_6 \leq b_6 \leq a_7 \leq b_7$

$$\mu_A(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z-a_1}{a_2-a_1} \right] & a_1 \leq z \leq a_2 \\ \frac{1}{2} & a_2 \leq z \leq a_3 \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z-a_3}{a_4-a_3} \right] & a_3 \leq z \leq a_4 \\ 1 & z = a_4 \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{a_5-z}{a_5-a_4} \right] & a_4 \leq z \leq a_5 \\ \frac{1}{2} & a_5 \leq z \leq a_6 \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{a_7-z}{a_7-a_6} \right] & a_6 \leq z \leq a_7 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\gamma_A(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z-b_1}{b_2-b_1} \right] & b_1 \leq z \leq b_2 \\ \frac{1}{2} & b_2 \leq z \leq b_3 \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z-b_3}{b_4-b_3} \right] & b_3 \leq z \leq b_4 \\ 1 & z = b_4 \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{b_5-z}{b_5-b_4} \right] & b_4 \leq z \leq b_5 \\ \frac{1}{2} & b_5 \leq z \leq b_6 \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{b_7-z}{b_7-b_6} \right] & b_6 \leq z \leq b_7 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Figure-2 Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Number

Definition 2.5

If X be a non-empty set then the **fuzzy multi set** A on X is defined as $A = \{(z, \mu_A^1(z), \mu_A^2(z), \dots, \mu_A^n(z)) / z \in X\}$, whereand this membership function maps each element of X to a membership value between 0 and 1 $\exists \mu_A^1(z) \geq \mu_A^2(z) \geq \dots \geq \mu_A^n(z)$ for $z \in X$

Definition 2.6

Let X be a non-empty set A , **intuitionistic fuzzy multi set** on X is defined as $A = \{(z, (\mu_A^1(z), \mu_A^2(z), \dots, \mu_A^n(z)), (\gamma_A^1(z), \gamma_A^2(z), \dots, \gamma_A^n(z))) / z \in X\}$ such that $0 \leq \mu_A^n(z) + (\gamma_A^n(z)) \leq 1$

Definition 2.7

The **Cardinality** of the membership function $Mc(z)$ and the non-membership function $N Mc(z)$ is the length of an element x in an *IFMS* A denoted as η , defined as $\eta = |Mc(z)| = |NMc(z)|$
 If $A, B,$ and C are the *IFMS* defined on X , then their cardinality $\eta = \text{Max} \{\eta(A), \eta(B), \eta(C)\}$.

Definition 2.8

A **heptagonal fuzzy multi number** is specified by 7 tuples $A_H = (a_1^i, a_2^i, a_3^i, a_4^i, a_5^i, a_6^i, a_7^i)$ where $a_1^i, a_2^i, a_3^i, a_4^i, a_5^i, a_6^i$ and a_7^i are real numbers and $a_1^i \leq a_2^i \leq a_3^i \leq a_4^i \leq a_5^i \leq a_6^i \leq a_7^i$

$$\mu_A(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z - a_1^i}{a_2^i - a_1^i} \right] & a_1^i \leq z \leq a_2^i \\ \frac{1}{2} & a_2^i \leq z \leq a_3^i \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z - a_2^i}{a_3^i - a_2^i} \right] & a_3^i \leq z \leq a_4^i \\ 1 & z = a_4^i \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{a_5^i - z}{a_5^i - a_4^i} \right] & a_4^i \leq z \leq a_5^i \\ \frac{1}{2} & a_5^i \leq z \leq a_6^i \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{a_7^i - z}{a_7^i - a_6^i} \right] & a_6^i \leq z \leq a_7^i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Figure-3 Heptagonal Fuzzy Multi Number

Definition 2.8

A **Heptagonal intuitionistic fuzzy multi number** is specified by 7 tuples $A_H=(a_1^i, a_2^i, a_3^i, a_4^i, a_5^i, a_6^i, a_7^i), (b_1^i, b_2^i, b_3^i, b_4^i, b_5^i, b_6^i, b_7^i)$ where $a_1^i, a_2^i, a_3^i, a_4^i, a_5^i, a_6^i, a_7^i, b_1^i, b_2^i, b_3^i, b_4^i, b_5^i, b_6^i, b_7^i$ are real numbers and $b_1^i \leq a_1^i \leq b_2^i \leq a_2^i \leq b_3^i \leq a_3^i \leq b_4^i = a_4^i \leq a_5^i \leq b_5^i \leq a_6^i \leq b_6^i \leq a_7^i \leq b_7^i$

$$\mu_A(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z - a_1^i}{a_2^i - a_1^i} \right] & a_1^i \leq z \leq a_2^i \\ \frac{1}{2} & a_2^i \leq z \leq a_3^i \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z - a_2^i}{a_3^i - a_2^i} \right] & a_3^i \leq z \leq a_4^i \\ 1 & z = a_4^i \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{a_5^i - z}{a_5^i - a_4^i} \right] & a_4^i \leq z \leq a_5^i \\ \frac{1}{2} & a_5^i \leq z \leq a_6^i \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{a_7^i - z}{a_7^i - a_6^i} \right] & a_6^i \leq z \leq a_7^i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\gamma_A(z) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z - b_1^i}{b_2^i - b_1^i} \right] & b_1^i \leq z \leq b_2^i \\ \frac{1}{2} & b_3^i \leq z \leq b_4^i \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{z - b_2^i}{b_3^i - b_2^i} \right] & b_3^i \leq z \leq b_4^i \\ 0 & z = b_4^i \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{b_5^i - z}{b_5^i - b_4^i} \right] & b_4^i \leq z \leq b_5^i \\ \frac{1}{2} & b_5^i \leq z \leq b_6^i \\ 1 - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{b_7^i - z}{b_7^i - b_6^i} \right] & b_6^i \leq z \leq b_7^i \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Figure-4 Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number

3. Ranking Measures Of Heptagonal intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Numbers

Many Ranking Measures are available for Intuitionistic Fuzzy Numbers (*IFN*), where the membership and non-membership functions are considered only once. But, in Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Numbers (*IFMN*) because of their multi membership and non-membership functions, it should be considered more than once. And, their considerations are combined together by means of Summation concept based on their cardinality.

Few new Ranking Measures for the Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number (*HIFMN*) are proposed in this section. The **Graded Mean Representation Method, Helipern’s Expected Value Method, Sub Interval Average Method, Proposed Method, Extended Method, Active Method, Accuracy Function-Based Method, Sign Ranking Distance Method of HIFMNs** were presented.

Method I: Graded Mean Integration

The Ranking Measure by the **Graded Mean Integration Representation** of Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number (*HIFMN*) A_i is defined for as follows

$$R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \max \left[\frac{a_1^i + a_2^i + a_3^i + 4a_4^i + a_5^i + a_6^i + a_7^i}{10}, \frac{b_1^i + b_2^i + b_3^i + 4b_4^i + b_5^i + b_6^i + b_7^i}{10} \right]$$

Method II: Helipern’s Expected Value

Here, another method using the **Heilpern’s Expected Value** using the notions of the expected value is introduced. These are based on the lower and upper expected values of A_i , Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number for heptagonal with its membership and non-membership functions is defined as follows

$$R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \max \left[\frac{a_1^i + a_2^i + a_3^i + 2a_4^i + a_5^i + a_6^i + a_7^i}{8}, \frac{b_1^i + b_2^i + b_3^i + 2b_4^i + b_5^i + b_6^i + b_7^i}{8} \right]$$

Method III: Sub Interval Average

Another Ranking Measure based on **Sub-Interval Average** for Ranking of Linear Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number A_i is also proposedas follows:

$$R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \max \left[\frac{a_1^i + a_2^i + a_3^i + a_4^i + a_5^i + a_6^i + a_7^i}{7}, \frac{b_1^i + b_2^i + b_3^i + b_4^i + b_5^i + b_6^i + b_7^i}{7} \right]$$

Method IV: Accuracy Function Based

Another Ranking Measure based on **Accuracy Function-Based Method** for ranking Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number A_i is proposedas follows:

$$R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{a_1^i + a_2^i + a_3^i + a_4^i + a_5^i + a_6^i + a_7^i + b_1^i + b_2^i + b_3^i + b_4^i + b_5^i + b_6^i + b_7^i}{7} \right]$$

Method V: Active Ranking Measure

Another Active Ranking Measure of Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number A_i is proposedas,

$$R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{a_1^i + a_2^i + a_3^i + 2a_4^i + a_5^i + a_6^i + a_7^i + b_1^i + b_2^i + b_3^i + 2b_4^i + b_5^i + b_6^i + b_7^i}{16} \right]$$

Method VI: Extended Ranking Measure

Extended Ranking Measure of Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number A_i based on is proposed as follows:

$$R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \max [A_{\mu}^i, A_{\theta}^i] \text{ where}$$

$$A_{\mu}^i = \frac{2a_1^i + 3a_2^i + 4a_3^i + 5a_4^i + 4a_5^i + 3a_6^i + 2a_7^i}{23} \text{ and } A_{\theta}^i = \frac{2b_1^i + 3b_2^i + 4b_3^i + 5b_4^i + 4b_5^i + 3b_6^i + 2b_7^i}{23}$$

Method VII: Sign Ranking Distance

The Ranking Measures of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number A_i based on **Sign Distance Measures** are defined below for heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number

$$R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n R(A_i) \text{ where, } R(A_i) = \left[\frac{a_7^i - a_1^i}{b_7^i - b_1^i} \right] D(A_i) \text{ so that}$$

$$D(A_i) = \left[\frac{a_1^i + a_2^i + a_3^i + 4a_4^i + a_5^i + a_6^i + a_7^i + b_1^i + b_2^i + b_3^i + 4b_4^i + b_5^i + b_6^i + b_7^i}{16} \right]$$

The two Ranking measures, Graded Mean Integration Representation Method and Expected Value Method of the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Numbers leads to proposal of other Five Ranking Measure of *HIFMNs*. By the introduced Ranking Measures, the *HIFMNs* are transformed to crisp data, which can used for any multi criteria decision making problems.

4 Numerical Illustrations Of *Hifmnr* ranking Measures

The introduced Ranking Measures of *HIFMNs* with its membership and non-membership function for the Heptagonal Numbers from the extension for fuzzy ranking measures. The efficiency of the Ranking Techniques is analysed with the numerical examples, and it is clear that all these methods are well suited as their ranking measures are closer to one another.

$$A = \{(1,3,5,6,7,9,11) (0,2,4,6,8,10,12);$$

$$(0,2,4,5,6,7,9) (0,1,3,5,6,8,10);$$

$$(2,4,6,7,8,10,11) (1,3,5,7,9,10,12);$$

$$(1,4,6,8,10,11,13) (0,2,5,8,10,12,13)\},$$

$$B = \{(2,4,6,7,8,10,11) (0,3,5,7,8,10,12);$$

$$(1,3,5,7,9,10,12) (0,2,4,7,9,11,13);$$

$$(0,2,4,5,7,9,10) (0,1,4,5,8,9,11)\};$$

$(1,3,4,7,8,10,12) (0,2,4,7,9,11,12)\}$

$C=\{(1,4,6,8,10,11,12) (0,2,5,8,10,11,13);$

$(1,3,4,7,8,10,12) (0,2,4,7,9,11,12);$

$(1,2,4,6,9,11,12) (0,2,3,6,10,11,13);$

$(1,3,5,7,9,10,12) (0,2,4,7,9,11,13)\}$ and

$D=\{(5,7,8,9,10,12,13) (4,6,8,9,11,12,14);$

$(6,7,8,9,11,13,14) (5,6,7,9,12,13,15);$

$(5,6,8,10,12,14,16) (4,5,7,10,13,14,16);$

$(4,5,7,10,11,13,14) (3,4,6,10,12,13,15)\}$ is defined in the following tabular column **Table 4.1** for the methods which are discussed above and this shows that these measures are suited for any decision-making applications.

Heptagonal IFMN	A	B	C	D	Rank
Method-1	6.3	6.4	6.8	9.5	$A < B < C < D$
Method-2	6.3	6.4	6.7	9.5	$A < B < C < D$
Method-3	6.3	6.4	6.8	9.5	$A < B < C < D$
Method-4	12.4	12.5	13.3	18.9	$A < B < C < D$
Method-5	6.3	6.3	6.7	9.5	$A = B < C < D$
Method-6	6.4	6.2	6.8	9.5	$B < A < C < D$
Method-7	6.7	6.5	7.1	10.02	$B < A < C < D$

Table 4.1 : Heptagonal IFMN Ranking

5. Analysis Of The Ranking Measure

Definition 5.1

The properties of the general ranking measures are

- I. $R(A_i) > 0$
- II. $R(A_i, B_i) > 0 \leftrightarrow R(A_i) > R(B_i) \leftrightarrow A_i > B_i$
- III. $R(A_i, B_i) < 0 \leftrightarrow R(A_i) < R(B_i) \leftrightarrow A_i < B_i$
- IV. $R(A_i, B_i) = 0 \leftrightarrow R(A_i) = R(B_i) \leftrightarrow A_i = B_i$

The ranking measures of *HIFMN* satisfies the properties of the ranking measure, even though, the seven extended ranking measures slightly in their formula they give the same result. To justify the

concept to analysis the properties, $A_i = \{(a_1^i, a_2^i, a_3^i, a_4^i, a_5^i, a_6^i, a_7^i), (b_1^i, b_2^i, b_3^i, b_4^i, b_5^i, b_6^i, b_7^i)\}$ in which the membership function is $a_1^i, a_2^i, a_3^i, a_4^i, a_5^i, a_6^i, a_7^i$ and the non-membership function $b_1^i, b_2^i, b_3^i, b_4^i, b_5^i, b_6^i, b_7^i$ are real numbers of *HIFMN*, the following numerical examples are considered.

Example 5.1

The *HIFMN* set A defined below consist of four elements, hence its cardinality is 4

$$A = \{(1,3,5,7,9,10,12)(0,2,4,7,9,11,13);$$

$$(1,2,4,6,9,11,12)(0,2,3,6,10,11,13);$$

$$(1,3,4,7,8,10,12)(0,2,4,7,9,11,13);$$

$$(1,4,6,8,10,11,12)(0,2,5,8,10,13)\}$$

Here, $R(A) > 0$, the property one is verified

Example 5.2

The *HIFMN* sets A, B defined below consist of four elements, results the cardinality as 4

$$A = \{(1,3,5,7,9,10,12)(0,2,4,7,9,11,13);$$

$$(1,2,4,6,9,11,12)(0,2,3,6,10,11,13);$$

$$(1,3,4,7,8,10,12)(0,2,4,7,9,11,13);$$

$$(1,4,6,8,10,11,12)(0,2,5,8,10,13)\}$$

$$B = \{(2,4,6,7,8,10,11)(1,3,5,7,9,10,12);$$

$$(0,2,4,5,6,7,9)(0,1,3,5,6,8,10);$$

$$(1,4,6,8,10,11,13)(0,2,5,8,10,12,13);$$

$$(1,3,5,6,7,9,11)(0,2,4,6,8,10,12)\}$$

That is, $R(A_i, B_i) > 0 \leftrightarrow R(A_i) > R(B_i) \leftrightarrow A_i > B_i$. Hence the property two is verified

Example 5.3

The *HIFMN* sets A, B defined is of four elements of cardinality 4

$$A = \{(0,2,4,5,7,9,10)(0,1,4,5,8,9,11);$$

$$(1,3,4,7,8,10,12)(0,2,4,7,9,11,12);$$

$$(2,4,6,7,8,10,11)(0,3,5,7,8,10,12);$$

$$(1,3,5,7,9,10,12)(0,2,4,7,9,11,13)\}$$
 and

$$B = \{(5,7,8,9,10,12,13)(4,6,8,9,11,12,14);$$

(6,7,8,9,11,13,14)(5,6,7,9,12,13,15);
 (5,6,8,10,12,14,16)(4,5,7,10,13,14,16);
 (4,5,7,10,11,13,14)(3,4,6,10,12,13,15)}

Here, $R(A) > R(B) \leftrightarrow A > B$, (i.e.) the property three is verified

Example 5.4

$A = \{(1,3,4,7,8,10,12)(0,2,4,7,9,11,12);$
 $(0,2,4,5,7,9,10)(0,1,4,5,8,9,11);$
 $(2,4,6,7,8,10,11)(1,3,5,7,9,10,12);$
 $(4,5,7,10,11,13,14)(3,4,6,10,12,13,15)\}$ and

$B = \{(0,4,5,7,8,10,12)(0,3,5,7,9,11,12);$
 $(0,1,3,5,7,9,10)(0,1,3,5,7,9,10);$
 $(2,4,6,7,8,10,11)(1,3,5,7,9,10,12);$
 $(4,5,6,7,10,11,13,14)(3,4,6,10,12,13,16)\}$

Here, $R(A_i, B_i) = 0 \leftrightarrow R(A_i) = R(B_i) \leftrightarrow A_i = B_i$ Hence the property four is verified

Example 5.5

Now, five *HIFMN*s namely A,B,C,D,E are considered in random, each *HIFMN* having the cardinality of 4. The obtained result is ranked as $B < D < E < A < C$ based on the crisp value.

	<i>HIFMN</i> value	Crispvalue
A	{(1,4,6,8,10,11,12) (0,2,5,8,10,11,13); (1,3,4,7,8,10,11,12) (0,2,4,7,9,11,12); (1,2,4,6,9,11,12) (0,2,3,6,10,11,13); (1,3,5,7,9,10,12) (0,2,4,7,9,11,13)}	2
B	{(1,3,5,6,7,9,11) (0,2,4,6,8,10,12); (0,2,4,5,6,7,9) (0,1,3,5,6,8,10); (2,4,6,7,8,10,11) (1,3,5,7,9,10,12); (1,4,6,8,10,11,13) (0,2,5,8,10,12,13)}	5
C	{(5,7,8,9,10,12,13)(4,6,8,9,10,12,13); (6,7,8,9,11,13,14)(5,6,7,9,12,13,15); (5,6,8,10,12,14,16)(4,5,7,10,13,14,16); (4,5,7,10,11,13,14)(3,4,6,10,12,13,15)}	1
D	{(2,4,6,7,8,10,11)(0,3,5,7,8,10,12); (1,3,5,7,9,10,12)(0,2,4,7,9,11,12);	4

	(1,2,4,6,9,11,12)(0,2,3,6,10,11,13); (1,3,5,7,9,10,12)(0,2,4,7,9,11,13)}	
E	{(4,5,7,10,11,13,14)(3,4,6,10,12,13,15); (0,2,4,5,6,7,9)(0,1,3,5,6,8,10); (1,3,4,7,8,10,12)(0,2,4,7,9,11,12); (1,3,5,6,7,9,11)(0,2,4,6,8,10,12)}	3

6. Conclusion

Seven measures of the Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number were introduced. By the introduced Ranking Measures, the *HIFMNs* are transformed to crisp data, which can be used for any multi criteria decision making problem. Ranking measures defined with the membership and non-membership function satisfies all the properties of ranking condition which were analysed with the numerical examples. And, it is clear that all the seven measures results are closer to one another and hence these measures are suited for any multi decision-making applications.

References

- [1] **Adilakshmi Siripurapu, Ravi Shankar Nowpada**, *A New Ranking In Heptagonal Fuzzy Number And its Application in Project Scheduling* RT&A, No 2 (68) Volume 17, June 2022
- [2] **Atanassov K** *Intuitionistic fuzzy sets*. Physica-Verlag A Springer-Verlag Company, New York(1999).
- [3] **J.G. Dijkman, H. Van Haeringen, and S. J. De Lange**, *Fuzzy Numbers* Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications 92, 301-341 (1983)
- [4] **R. Jain**, "A procedure for multi-aspect decision making using fuzzy sets," International Journal of Systems Science, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–7, 1977.
- [5] **Rajarajeswari P, Uma N** (2013) *On distance and similarity measures of intuitionistic fuzzy multi set*. IOSR Journal of Mathematics (IOSR-JM) e-ISSN: 2278-5728. Volume 5, Issue 4 (Jan=Feb. 2013), PP 19-23
- [6] **Rajarajeswari P, Uma N** (2014) *Correlation measure for intuitionistic fuzzy multi sets*. International journal of Research in Engineering and technology 3(1):611-617
- [7] **Rajarajeswari P, Uma N** (2014) *Zhang and Fuz similarity measure on intuitionistic fuzzymulti sets*. International journal of Research in Engineering and technology 3(5):12309–12317 .
- [8] **Shan-Huo Chen**, *Ranking fuzzy numbers with maximizing set and minimizing set*, Fuzzy Sets and Systems Volume 17, Issue 2, November 1985, Pages 113-129

- [9] **Shinoj TK, John SJ** (2012) *Intuitionistic fuzzy multisets and its application in medical diagnosis*. World academy of science and technology 6(1):1418–1421
- [10] **Shinoj TK, Sunil JJ** (2013) *Accuracy in collaborative robotics: an intuitionistic fuzzy multiset approach*. Global journal of science frontier research Mathematics and decision sciences 13(10):21-28
- [11] **E. Vivek**, *Ranking measure of fuzzy multi numbers*, Indian journal of science, Volume-14, October 2023
- [12] **Yager RR** (1986), *On the theory of bags*. International Journal of General System 13:23–37.
- [13] **L.A.Zadeh**, *Fuzzy sets*, Information and Control , Volume 8 (1965), 338-353

Cite this article

***Gokul Priyan. A, **Uma. N, “On Ranking Measures of Heptagonal Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Number”** Scholastic Bazillion: Journal Of Multidisciplinary Studies, Vol.1, Issue 1, January 2024, pp. 46-59